

Anti-mobbing Technology in the Conditions of an Educational Institution in Ukraine

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Abstract: *The article reveals the essence of the concept "mobbing" and its classification in the context of pedagogical management. An empirical study has been conducted to identify the presence, frequency, causes, features of manifestations and consequences of mobbing processes in the teaching staff of general secondary education in Ukraine. Methods of randomized experiment, correlation analysis, scaling and ranking were used to process the research results. The results of the correlation analysis revealed causal relationships between some causes, manifestations, consequences of mobbing and certain statistical characteristics. The results of the empirical study prove the presence and prevalence of cases of mobbing in the teaching staff of secondary schools in Ukraine. The results of the study allow us to conclude that in general secondary education institutions, depending on the status of the persons involved, all three types of mobbing are implemented. Vertical prevails - 41.5%. Horizontal - 27.7% of respondents, mixed - 11.8%. 19% of respondents did not face mobbing. Depending on the specifics of harassment, there are different variations of mobbing processes, which sometimes overlap in their manifestations. Bosing prevails - 41.5%. 27.7% indicated bullying, social isolation - 15.8%, staffing - 14.7%, sandwich mobbing - 11.8%, gaslighting - 8.4%, outing - 7.7%, ageism - 6.8%, stalking - 5.9%, cyber mobbing - 4.7%. Also, based on the results of the survey, we can conclude that in educational institutions there are manifestations of obstruction - 3.1% of respondents. The general bases of anti-mobbing technology have been developed - a system of measures of the head and pedagogical workers to prevent, detect and combat harassment, moral pressure, psychological terror in an educational institution.*

Keywords: *Educational institution; head; mobbing; pedagogical management; pedagogical workers.*

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1. Introduction

In modern conditions of increasing stratification of society, non-observance of generally accepted norms of relationships in work collectives has become widespread, accompanied by moral persecution and pressure in the workplace. Therefore, a serious problem that has been actively discussed in recent years by scientists and personnel managers is the problem of mobbing as a form of regular bullying, humiliation, pressure, terror, demonstration of neglect, isolation of an employee by a head, colleague or team.

To date, this problem has reached global proportions. Studies conducted in different countries indicate that many workers in various fields suffer from moral humiliation, psychological terror, harassment and bullying in the workplace. According to the American scientist G. Namie (2014), 27% of workers have experienced psychological terror in the workplace, 72% - confirm the fact that harassment in the workforce occurs regularly. International research by G. Macassa et al. (2013) showed that 29.7% of Swedes, 27.1% of Germans, 24.6% of Lithuanians and 21.9% of Portuguese experienced psychological terror. Significantly lower results of the mobbing phenomenon (11.6% of respondents) were shown by a survey of Turkish researchers E. Yelgecen-Tigrel, & O. Kokalan (2009). However, in Nigeria and Oman, the rate is very high at 77% (Ogunsemi et al., 2010), and in some cases up to 97% (Al-Shafae, et al. 2013). As for Ukraine, according to the results of a survey conducted by L.V.Shchetinina, S.H.Rudakova, & K.O.Drobynska (2018) - 77% of Ukrainians in the workplace have personally encountered this negative phenomenon.

At the same time, K.H. Rekosh (2002) confirms that the prevalence of mobbing in education is much higher than in other areas of activity. In addition, in 90% of occasion, according to the scientist, the moral persecution is initiated by the head of the educational institution. And this indicates that the problem of mobbing in the educational environment in today's conditions is particularly acute.

Effective management of teaching staff will provide a safe, free from violence and harassment educational environment, comfortable interpersonal and professional relationships between the head and teachers. Therefore, the priority factors that contribute to the effective management of teaching staff are the established corporate culture and a favorable moral and psychological climate in the staff of the educational institution. Accordingly, this problem needs a thorough study in the context of effective management of teachers.

2. Literature review

Mobbing is one of the hotly debated problems in psychology, pedagogy, management, sociology, law, and medicine. Significant contributions to the research of this phenomenon have been made by such foreign researchers as: D. Chappell & V. Di Martino (2006), M. Duffy & L. Sperry (2013), C. Kolodej (2005), H. Leymann (1996), K. Lorents (1994), D. Olweus (2002), L. Waniorek & A. Waniorek (1994), D. Zapf (1999).

In the book *Violence at Work*, published by the International Labor Organization, mobbing is listed on a par with murder, rape and robbery, indicating its far-reaching negative and devastating consequences for the worker (Chappell & Martino, 2006).

For Ukraine, mobbing is a relatively new phenomenon that scientists have only begun to research since the second decade of the 21st century. In Ukrainian scientific sources, softer phrases "psychological pressure", "moral humiliation", "discrimination against an employee", "harassment in the workplace" are more often mentioned, but there are also more severe ones - "psychological terror", "psychological violence" (Serdyuk & Shupta, 2013).

Among Ukrainian scientists, the problem of mobbing was investigated by: O. V. Adamchuk (2014), N.O. Alyushina (2019), T. M. Dzyuba (2017), O.V. Kachmar (2016), H. Leshchuk (2015), A.I. Marenich & Vovk (2015), O.B. Oros (2020), O.I. Serdyuk & I.M. Shupta (2013), O.T. Smuk (2018), L.V. Shchetinina (2018), etc.

The purpose of this research was to study the mobbing processes in the system of interpersonal and professional relationships of the head and teachers of the general secondary education institution of Ukraine; outlining the general foundations of anti-mobbing technology in the context of pedagogical management.

3. Theoretical Basis

In the modern sense, the term "mobbing" was first used by the Swedish scientist H. Leiman, who in the early 80's of the twentieth century studied the peculiarities of human behavior in the team. The scientist described this phenomenon as psychological terror, which includes the systematic repeated hostile and unethical behavior of one or more people directed against another person. He believed that mobbing existed when at least once a week the victim was oppressed in any form of discrimination for six months or more. He called the main manifestations of mobbing: information concealment, mudslinging, social isolation, continuous criticism, gossip, ridicule, etc. (Leymann, 1996).

Having carried out an interdisciplinary analysis of the definitions of the key concept of this study and adapting it to pedagogical management, we consider mobbing as causing moral harm in the workplace; destructive strategy of behavior of pedagogical staff of an educational institution, which leads to a sharp interpersonal conflict with colleagues, head or other entities, which differs in its specificity, systematicity and duration, and is directed against an individual pedagogical employee.

The object of mobbing is the victim of harassment, the subject is the mobster - a person who commits mobbing actions against a particular employee.

A young specialist, an experienced professional, and a woman of retirement age can become a victim of educational mobbing. Thus, mobbing in an educational institution is possible both vertically (the head - the subordinate), and horizontally (workers of one rank).

In the modern scientific literature, mobbing in the system of social and labor relations is classified according to various characteristics, which we have adapted to educational institutions. Accordingly, mobbing is classified as:

- 1) Depending on the status of the persons involved:
 - horizontal - psychological terror, moral humiliation by colleagues;
 - vertical - psychological terror, which is carried out in the plane of "head-staff";
 - mixed - simultaneous harassment of an employee by a manager and a colleague.
- 2) Depending on the specifics of harassment:
 - bossing - pressure of the head of the educational institution on the subordinate, systematic unfair criticism of the pedagogical worker with an indication of his/her professional incompetence, humiliation of his/her dignity;
 - staffing - collective pressure on the leader from subordinates;
 - sandwich mobbing - parallel pressure on the employee from both the manager and colleagues;
 - cyber mobbing (trolling) - harassment of a colleague using modern information and communication technologies (through a global or local network of an educational institution, social networks, phone calls, personal messages);
 - stalking - obsessive, undesirable and constant harassment of one employee by another;
 - outing - public disclosure of information compromising the victim, which may eventually lead to harassment;

- ageism - the creation of stereotypes and discrimination against individual employees on the basis of age;

- gaslighting - manipulation, the purpose of which is to make the victim doubt the adequacy of their perception of the surrounding reality, questioning their own sanity, professionalism;

- obstruction - counteraction to the normal work of the pedagogical council, methodical meeting, etc.;

- social isolation of the employee - a social phenomenon in which there is a removal of a teacher or several employees from a group of colleagues or the team as a whole as a result of termination or sharp reduction of social contacts and interactions, ignoring.

3) Depending on the number of entities that carry out mobbing actions: individual, group, collective.

4) Depending on the subject's awareness of mobbing actions: conscious, unconscious, controlled.

5) Depending on the form of manifestation: latent, open (Soroka, 2013).

Regarding the causes, forms of manifestations and consequences of mobbing processes in general secondary education institutions of Ukraine, their variability was determined by us in the course of experimental research.

4. Methodology and research methods

We conducted research on mobbing in the teaching staff of general secondary education institutions of Ukraine during October-December 2020. The research method is an anonymous online survey through the Google Forms cloud service. Questionnaires were distributed through the social network Facebook, namely through 46 educational communities (groups). We believe that online questioning of this extremely complex problem is the most appropriate, as direct, face-to-face contact directly with respondents in educational institutions would not give proper openness in the answers. The collection and analysis of such anonymous information will help to understand how often and under what circumstances a pedagogical worker of Ukraine gets into a mobbing situation.

Methods of randomized approach, correlation analysis (Pearson's correlation coefficient), scaling and ranking were used in processing the survey results. Statistical and mathematical calculations were automated using Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and Google Sheets cloud service.

5. Results

An empirical study was conducted to identify the presence, frequency, causes, features of manifestations and consequences of mobbing processes in the teaching staff of general secondary education in Ukraine.

The general population of the study were pedagogical staff of general secondary education institutions of Ukraine (without disclosing the name of the institution). The total number of respondents is 1000 respondents. The representativeness of the sample was determined by random sampling. The error with a probability of 0.95 depending on the sample size is 3.1%.

The study used the author's questionnaire "Mobbing in the teaching staff" (2020). Respondents who took part in the survey were divided into three categories: "A" - heads (directors) of general secondary education institutions (7.4%); "B" - deputies for educational, upbringing or educational work (16.1%); "B" - teachers, teaching assistants, educators, teachers-organizers, practical psychologists, social educators, leaders of clubs, sections, studios, etc. (76.5%).

According to the geographical location, the participants were divided into five regions of Ukraine: Central (29.8%), Western (24.5%), Eastern (15.7%), Northern (11%) and Southern (19%).

By gender, 89.3% of women and 10.7% of men took part in the survey. Such gender inequality in the teaching staff in general secondary education institutions of Ukraine is an established norm. Work experience of respondents: 0-2 years - 2.5%, 3-10 years - 20.5%, 11-20 years - 28.3%, 21-30 years - 31.5%, 31 and more years - 17, 2%. These results are specific to the educational sphere: the vast majority of women with 11-30 years of experience (55.6%).

Regarding qualification categories, the respondents were: 12.6% - specialists, 13.3% - category II employees, 23.4% - category I employees, 50.7% - higher category. 32.6% of respondents have pedagogical titles.

As a result of the survey, it was found that the vast majority of teachers have sufficient (53.9%) and average (23.7%) levels of awareness about the phenomenon of mobbing.

According to the results of the analysis of the obtained data, it was revealed that 81% (810 people) of pedagogical workers encountered mobbing in an educational institution, and 19% did not encounter. At the same time, 490 respondents (49% of the total number of respondents) indicated that they acted as victims in mobbing processes. 18.3% (183 people) of respondents appeared as defenders of the victim, and 10.4% (104 people) - passively watched the mobbing process and did not take any

action. Only 3.3% (33 people) admitted to acting as mobsters (or mobsters' accomplices). The latter data are considered by us to be obviously false. Because the aggressors themselves cannot always admit that they are carrying out psychological terror against someone. It is clear that in reality this figure is many times higher.

Frequency of teachers' bullying was: every day (35%), once a week (24%), once a month (16%), rarely (6%), never (19%).

Regarding the main subjects (mobsters) of mobbing actions, the results of the survey are as follows:

Fig. 1. Subjects of mobbing actions in general secondary education institutions of Ukraine, (source: calculated by the authors on the basis of data)

It is projected that in the vast majority of cases the subject of mobbing was the head of the educational institution or one of his/her deputies (41.5%), much less often - together with colleagues (4.8%). Quite a high percentage of mobbing processes in the teaching staff is implemented by a group of colleagues (17.1%) and a single colleague -10.6%. It is rare for mobbing actions against the victim to be carried out by the entire teaching staff (1.5%).

The specificity of mobbing in the education system lies in the fact that not direct opponents, but also other people (applicants for education, their parents, etc.) can be drawn to it. In addition, they directly and indirectly negatively affect the perception of teaching staff by those around them, that is, they have anti-educational consequences. There are relatively few such cases: students (1.9%) and parents of students (3.6%).

To solve the problem of the mobbing process, to identify the reasons that led to its emergence, is the primary task of the head of the educational institution. Respondents identified objective and subjective reasons for mobbing, which determine its belonging to a destructive conflict. The variation of causes is quite large. Table 1 lists the reasons most debated by the respondents, which we ranked in descending order of the frequency of their mention in the questionnaires.

Table 1. Diagnosis of the frequency of causes of mobbing in general secondary education institutions of Ukraine

The cause of mobbing	%	Number of respondents
The need for leadership or dominance of a person over colleagues	56,7%	567
Envy	45,0%	450
Personal rejection of a person	35,5%	355
Ambitions, aspirations for career growth	28,4%	284
Competition	24,2%	242
Free up space "for cronies"	24,0%	240
Restriction of status, manipulation in the team	23,4%	234
The desire for revenge	21,4%	214
Professional incompetence	21,2%	212
Corruption	15,2%	152
Change of management (violation of the established rules of the team)	14,7%	147
Weakness, emotional instability of the individual, inability to defend their interests, constructively resolve the conflict	13,2%	132
Extraordinary personality	12,0%	120
Fears	7,1%	71
Discrimination against individual employees on the basis of age	6,8%	68
Boredom	2,8%	28
Do not know the reason	2,7%	27

(Source: calculated by the authors on the basis of data)

The reasons for the use of mobbing actions in the complex determine its specific type and form of manifestation in relation to the victim. Manifestations of mobbing actions encountered by teachers in general secondary education are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Diagnosis of the frequency of mobbing in general secondary education institutions in Ukraine

Manifestations of mobbing	%	Number of respondents
Constant unsubstantiated criticism and unsatisfactory assessment of work by management, excessive meticulousness and checking of current work	52,5%	525
Attribution of success to other employees, non-recognition of achievements and successes, blocking the opportunity to move up the career ladder	45,2%	452
Verbal aggression (shouting, deliberate statements of others aimed at causing negative feelings, insults, threats, blackmail)	42,6%	426
Dissemination of rumors and unreliable information among the teaching staff, damage to the professional and business reputation of the employee	38,6%	386
Bullying in front of the whole staff	37,7%	377
Special communication with the victim of mobbing (e.g. interruption, not listening)	31,5%	315
Deliberate overburdening in comparison with other teachers and / or delegation of powers that do not correspond to the level of competence	29,2%	292
Unreasonable change or deterioration of working and leisure conditions (postponement of vacation to an inconvenient time, constant inclusion in the duty schedule, giving the worst classroom, deterioration of the conditions of material and technical support)	22,7%	227
Intentional restriction of access to necessary information	19,9%	199
Systematic deliberate bringing to tears	19,7%	197
Manipulating premiums	18,0%	180
Obscene jokes, comments	17,6%	176
Social isolation in the team, ignoring (are not invited to meetings, councils, corporate events, do not communicate, etc.)	15,8%	158
Systematic setting of the deadline, which prevents the proper execution of the order (tasks come with an unreasonably short deadline or after the deadline or at the end of the last day of the deadline)	9,8%	98
Public disclosure of compromising information	7,7%	77
Physical harassment during working and non-working hours (including by telephone)	5,9%	59
Damage to documents, working property, etc.	5,9%	59

Cyber mobbing (harassment on social networks)	4,7%	47
Suggestion of guilt and fear	3,8%	38
Opposition to the normal work of the pedagogical council, methodical meeting	3,1%	31

(Source: calculated by the authors on the basis of data)

Employees perceive mobbing differently in relation to themselves, tolerate and compensate for their pain in different ways. The consequences for the object (victim) of mobbing-actions, which the respondents observed in their pedagogical team or felt on themselves, can acquire such types, which are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Diagnosis of the frequency of consequences of mobbing processes in general secondary education institutions of Ukraine

Consequences of mobbing processes	%	Number of respondents
Deterioration of the microclimate in the team	70,0%	700
Increased anxiety, stress, phobias, depression, neurosis, sleep problems	69,1%	691
Inadequate perception of one's own individuality (low self-esteem, inferiority complex, insecurity)	44,6%	446
Social self-isolation within the educational organization (avoidance of colleagues)	38,4%	384
Dismissal	24,0%	240
Reduction in position, reduction of pedagogical load, removal of surcharges	23,0%	230
Aggressiveness	19,3%	193
Professional burnout	18,0%	180
Conformist behavior (adaptive acceptance of ready-made standards in behavior, unequivocal recognition of the existing state of affairs, laws, norms, rules, unconditional admiration for authorities)	16,1%	161
Inadequate perception of reality	8,4%	84
Addictive behavior (behavioral disorders resulting from the abuse of various substances that alter the mental state of a person)	3,9%	39
Suicidal behavior	1,8%	18

(Source: calculated by the authors on the basis of data)

It has been found that respondents who acted as victims (49%) still sought protection of their rights in the context of bullying of such individuals and legal entities (51.4%). 490 people who answered this question are considered as 100%.

Table 4. Diagnosis of the frequency of appeals from victims of mobbing processes to protect their rights to individuals and legal entities

Individuals and legal entities	%	Number of respondents
They did not apply anywhere	48,6%	486
To colleagues	12,2%	122
To the head (administration) of the educational institution	11,6%	116
To higher governing bodies in the field of education and science (city or district Department of Education, Department of Education and Science of the region, Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, Education Ombudsman Service, etc.)	11,4%	114
To the Primary Trade Union Organization	6,5%	65
To the psychologist	4,1%	41
To other human rights organizations	1,6%	16
Wrote a post about mobbing in their team in social networks	1,6%	16
To court	1,4%	14
To the police	0,8%	8
To the mediator	0,2%	2

(Source: calculated by the authors on the basis of data)

Of those who sought help in resolving the conflict, only 9.6% received it, and 34.9% received it in part. Unfortunately, in Ukraine, at the legislative level, there are no clear mechanisms for regulating mobbing.

6. Discussion

The results of the correlation analysis revealed causal relationships between some causes, manifestations, consequences of mobbing and certain statistical characteristics.

It has been found that regional affiliation, availability of qualification categories or pedagogical titles do not affect the frequency of mobbing processes.

Instead, we cut the opinions by job category and found a correlation. Thus, out of 490 respondents who indicated that they acted as victims in

mobbing processes, they belong to: category "A" - 12 respondents, which is 16.2% of the respondents in this category (74 took part in the survey); category "B" - 51, which is 31.7% of respondents in this category (161 took part in the survey); category "B" - 427, which is 55.8% of respondents in this category (765 took part in the survey). Figure 2 shows the frequency of the victim's role in the mobbing process by job category.

Fig. 2. Diagnosis of the frequency of mobbing actions in relation to the victim by job category, (source: calculated by the authors on the basis of data)

Thus, there is a clear correlation between the position and the role of the victim in the mobbing process (-0.7). The higher the position, the less likely you are to be a victim of mobbing in an educational institution. That is, there is a higher risk of harassment for teachers who hold positions in category "B" and less - in category "A".

It has been also found that the longer the teaching experience, the higher the risk of mobbing "Intentional overwork compared to other teachers and / or delegation of powers that do not correspond to the level of competence" (0.5).

Correlation analysis showed that women are more likely to be bullied in the teaching staff than men. That is, there is a positive correlation between gender and the role of the victim in mobbing processes (0.5).

It has also been found that mobbers use mobbing more often to teachers who work in an educational institution for up to three years than to others (out of 25 respondents from the category "0-2 years of teaching experience" - 20 victims, which is 80% of this category) .

Correlation analysis revealed a negative correlation (-0.7) between the use of mobbing and the continuation / termination of work in an educational institution. Thus, it has been statistically proven that mobbing is one of the factors in the turnover of teachers. In addition, the risk of dismissal of a teacher after mobbing increases if it is carried out by the head.

There is also a positive correlation between mobbing and envy among staff members (0.8); unhealthy competition (0.6); the need for leadership or dominance of a certain person over colleagues (0.85);

deterioration of the microclimate in the team (0.65); increased anxiety, stress, phobias, depression, neurosis, sleep problems (0.7), burnout (0.5).

Close correlations have been found between the causes and consequences of mobbing. In particular, the reason for "freeing up space for " insiders" correlates with the consequence of "dismissal" (-0.7); the reason "restriction of status, manipulation in the team" - with the consequence of "demotion, reduction of pedagogical workload, removal of surcharges" (-0.6); the reason is "weakness, emotional instability of the individual, inability to defend ones interests, constructively resolve the conflict" - with the consequence of "conformist behavior" (-0.55).

Positive correlations have been established between individuals and legal entities, to which teachers turn for protection of their own rights and some manifestations of harassment (0.6). This indicates that, depending on the manifestations of harassment, respondents choose to turn to the relevant individuals and legal entities.

The identified correlates prove that mobbing, stretched over time, is a special type of professional destruction, which causes a violation of the mechanisms of self-regulation, deformation of the internal picture of the health of the specialist, a negative impact on professional productivity.

The results of the study (in particular, the subjects, causes and manifestations of mobbing) allow us to conclude that in general secondary education institutions, depending on the status of the persons involved, all three types of mobbing are implemented. Vertical prevails - 41.5%. Horizontal - 27.7% of respondents, mixed - 11.8%. 19% of respondents did not face mobbing.

Depending on the specifics of harassment, there are different variations of mobbing processes, which sometimes overlap in their manifestations. Bosing prevails - 41.5%. 27.7% indicated bullying, social isolation - 15.8%, staffing - 14.7%, sandwich mobbing - 11.8%, gaslighting - 8.4%, outing - 7.7%, ageism - 6.8%, stalking - 5.9%, cyber mobbing - 4.7%. Also, based on the results of the survey, we can conclude that in educational institutions there are manifestations of obstruction - 3.1% of respondents.

Depending on the number of subjects who carry out mobbing actions: 52.1% of respondents indicated individual, 27.4% - group, collective - 1.5%.

Depending on the subject's awareness of mobbing, the results of statistical analysis indicate the advantage of deliberate harassment - 52.4%.

Depending on the form of manifestation - latent (hidden) psychological pressure prevails - 61%.

It is certain that the existence of mobbing in the teaching staff is the reason for the decline in the effective operation of any educational institution. Almost every second victim of mobbing (41.5%) suffers from the actions of the head (deputy) of the educational institution. In this case, it is quite difficult to help eliminate mobbing, and usually this process does not end in favor of the victim. But when the head acts as a subject of prevention and overcoming of mobbing, the chances of achieving justice increase many times over. To do this, one must have the technology to combat mobbing in the teaching staff (Marenych, 2015). Heads must constantly improve their leadership skills by introducing a high level of communication culture in the team, and under no circumstances allow inappropriate behavior towards colleagues or students. The ability of a manager to be a subject of prevention and overcoming of mobbing among subordinate personnel depends on ones readiness for such actions.

Unfortunately, managers (deputies) do not always contribute to the elimination of mobbing. Most of them look for a rational excuse, hide, underestimate or worse - just ignore. And only a small percentage of managers try to recognize, punish and eliminate this destructive phenomenon in their team.

With this in mind, we have developed anti-mobbing technology for the prevention of moral and psychological pressure in the team, which should be owned by the head of the educational institution. Accordingly, this technology is an important component of the author's course for future managers in the field of education "Pedagogical Management Technologies" (M.Shvardak), which is implemented under the master's educational program "Management of educational institutions" at Mukachevo State University (Ukraine).

We consider anti-mobbing technology as a system of consistent actions and instrumental support of management activities to prevent and combat mobbing in the teaching staff.

Preventing and overcoming mobbing among pedagogical staff of an educational institution is the direct responsibility of the head. First of all, it depends on the creation of an atmosphere in the team that promotes freedom and respect for the individual, initiative, fair remuneration for work, prevention of negative consequences of any conflicts, especially those arising from dissatisfaction with working conditions and communication (Sergienko, 2012).

The leader must understand the influence of different psychological states of a person on the work process; understand and be able to manage

conflicts in the team, which is necessary primarily to provide assistance to teachers who are in a state of stress and nervous crisis (Adamchuk, 2014).

The manager's ignorance of the essence of this issue, as well as the algorithm of actions, ways of solving it, causes the problem of the manager's unpreparedness to prevent and overcome mobbing among subordinates.

Therefore, anti-mobbing technology in general secondary education institutions is implemented according to the following algorithm:

1. Creating a safe educational environment in the educational institution, free from pressure, violence and harassment, creating conditions to prevent mobbing processes:

- introduction of a democratic style of leadership, humane managerial position of the leader-democrat;
- providing teachers with a real opportunity to openly express their views to management;
- adjusting teachers to independence and improving their level of professional competence;
- transparency of decision-making;
- emphasis on joint responsibility;
- application of a unified approach in incentives and penalties for teachers, regardless of subjective attitude;
- Clarification of the undesirable nature of mobbing and the application of sanctions if detected.

2. Diagnosis of interpersonal and professional relationships of pedagogical staff of an educational institution (anonymous questionnaire, personal interview - face-to-face).

3. Preventive work with the teaching staff:

- speeches at the pedagogical council on favorable interpersonal and professional relationships of pedagogical staff of the educational institution;
- "round tables" and workshops aimed at discussing the problem of mobbing in teaching staff;
- dialogue, restorative and mediation practices, anti-mobbing trainings.

4. Detection of mobbing in the teaching staff. Identification of active participants in mobbing actions (mobster, victim).

5. Finding out the reasons, identifying the manifestations of mobbing, a detailed study of the pressure situation from different angles.

6. Individual conversations with a mobster.

7. Prompt and competent separation of the victim with the corresponding stress effects.

8. Organization of psychological and corrective work with the victim of mobbing and the team in which the phenomenon arose to minimize the negative consequences:

- creating a climate of favorable moral and psychological comfort for the victim of mobbing to get a positive experience of support and trust;
- assistance in the formation of skills of confident behavior, adequate self-esteem, positive self-perception;
- promoting the development of constructive communication skills;
- minimization of the employee's feeling of loneliness by developing a sense of belonging to the team;
- increase the level of emotional comfort by reducing anxiety (Adamchuk, 2014).

9. Development and application of regulatory support for the regulation of relationships in the process of professional activity (additional provisions to the employment agreement). Development of rules that will ensure mutual respect between pedagogical staff of the educational institution. Destructive and antisocial behavior of any member of the team must be firmly and constantly condemned.

Studies of mobbing processes in general secondary education institutions in Ukraine provided an opportunity to formulate methodological advice to managers on preventing and combating mobbing:

- maintaining a favorable moral and psychological climate in the teaching staff;
- setting up constructive feedback "subordinates-manager";
- tough leadership position on gossipers and instigators of conflicts;
- clear formulation of job responsibilities of each employee, indicating the limits of their personal responsibility;
- formation of a system of personnel promotion and providing employees with career opportunities;
- exclusion of family or intimate ties between subordinates and management;
- the inadmissibility of the principle of dividing workers into "insiders" and "strangers";
- openness and transparency of information flows in the educational institution;
- formation of a transparent mechanism for making managerial decisions.

Effective tools for prevention and counteraction to mobbing in the conditions of general secondary education are: individual prevention of mobbing by the head and pedagogical workers; institutionalization of the

problem of mobbing (workshops aimed at discussing the problem of mobbing in teaching staff; development and implementation of organizational agreements); methods of intervention (psychological counseling, mediation, use of coping strategies, development of corporate culture of employees, psychological training, legal intervention, providing comprehensive assistance in dismissal).

7. Conclusions

Mobbing is a complex destructive phenomenon that causes stagnation of personal resources in an educational institution, is a sign of negative impact of the working atmosphere on the individual, causes regression of professional duties and increased turnover of teachers, creates unhealthy competition, worsens the health of teachers.

The results of the empirical study prove the presence and prevalence of cases of mobbing in the teaching staff of secondary schools in Ukraine (81% of teachers faced harassment in the workplace, of which 49% of respondents felt like victims).

From the analysis of statistical data it can be concluded that the most common types of this negative phenomenon are bossing (41.5%) and bullying (27.7%). The first occurs when the head of an educational institution, through abuse of power, puts pressure on an individual pedagogical worker or on the whole team. The latter consists in cruelty, humiliation of honor and dignity, unreasonable indication of professional incompetence on the part of the teaching staff.

In order to combat mobbing, we have developed anti-mobbing technology for heads of educational institutions, training with future heads of educational institutions "Antimobbing as an effective technology for creating a positive microclimate in the teaching staff."

The study does not cover all aspects of the problem. The direction of further scientific research may be the study of individual characteristics of objects and subjects of mobbing, the development of a model of combating mobbing in general secondary education institutions of Ukraine.

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